

Louis Vincent Tardent: a view from a different angle

In the XVIII century, the Russian government, interested in settling the lands captured from the Mongol nomads on the Volga and conquered from the Turks in the south of the country, needed diligent, capable specialists, and above all, the peasants. For this purpose, Empress Catherine II, and later Alexander I invited foreign immigrants. In 1762, the manifesto of Catherine II of December 4 declared: "... we allow all foreigners to enter our Empire and settle where anyone wishes in all our Provinces...". However, it had no success [9, P. 24].

On July 22, 1763, Catherine published her second, already revised manifesto. According to this manifesto, immigrants were promised large plots of land, exemption "for ever" from recruiting duties, as well as taxes for 30 years, an interest-free loan (to build houses, establish livestock, purchase agricultural equipment, supplies, etc.), which should be paid after 10 years, obtaining the right to engage in crafts, "to start factories and other necessary crafts, to trade, to join guilds and workshops, and everywhere to sell their products in the Empire"; settle in colonies, freely profess any religion, import their property duty free, etc. [9, P. 24-25].

This was the beginning of the "great migration of peoples" from European countries to Russia, which lasted about 100 years. It intensified in connection with the ruin of European countries by the Napoleonic wars. Germans, Swedes, Italians, Swiss and other nationalities rushed to Russia in a large flow [28, P. 25-30].

Foreign immigrants came mainly with entire families, and colonies were founded in the new place of residence.

One of these settlements was the Swiss colony of Chabag¹, formed in Bessarabia, in the south of the Russian Empire in 1822. Despite all the hardships that fell on the shoulders of the colonists, over time, in the 80s of the XIX century, Shabo became "the richest colony in Russia" [31, P. 38].

The issues of provisions for the formation of the Shabo colony, its origin and development in the first years of its existence were studied by a number of researchers (L. Gander, E.I. Druzhinina, H. Gander-Wolf, J. Tardent, O. Grivat, V.F. Onoprienko and others). - It is typical for the authors above that, one way or another, to assign a certain role to the person who they call the founder of the colony Louis Vincent Tardent. Here is a brief analysis of the publications of the above mentioned and other authors concerning this name.

In 1908, Louis Gander published an article [24] on the history of Shabo. It describes the preparation of the colonists for a long campaign, compiles a list of them, and also displays the first difficulties of the settlers on the way and in a new

1 Russian name Shabo.

place. Here L.V. Tardent is designated as one of the organizers of the risky event: “On August 13, 1820, we see him (*L. V. Tardent, note by author*) as a part of the first committee, whose responsibilities included determining of the location for the Shabo colony. On his side were winegrowers Jean Lucien Gerry, Georges Amelli Testu, Jacob Samuel Chevalley, Francois Louis Petit. The Assembly sent Tardent to explore the lands in distant Bessarabia, where Tsar Alexander I promised to allocate the fertile lands taken from Turkey” [24, P. 13].

The “Tardentiad” began in 1925 when a descendant of the Tardents, the French engineer A. Anselm published his letters, rewritten in 1922 in honor of the 100th anniversary of the Shabo colony [23] (Russian translation by V.F. Shishmaryov, 1979).

In the study by E.I. Druzhinina [10], the history of the Shabo colony, which occupies no more than 3 pages of text in the book, is considered as one of the many fragments of the development of the entire south of Ukraine. It shows only the main achievements of the colony and, of course, the analysis of the personality of the founder of the colony and the motives of his activities were not included in the author's plans. The same can be said about the article by M.A. Borodina ([3], 1964), to which E.I. Druzhinina repeatedly refers.

One of the most serious works on this issue seems to us to be the dissertation by H. Gander-Wolf [25], a significant part of which (paragraphs 2.1, 2.3) is devoted to the preparation for the formation of the colony and the time of the reign of the colony L.V. Tardan (1822-1831). H. Gander-Wolf substantiates the relevance of her work as follows (*abbreviated translation by the author*): 1) there is not a single detailed publication about Shabo, although there are many interesting short reports in newspapers and informational bulletins; 2) most of them depend on each other or have the form of a resume (generalization); 3) existing publications mainly describe life in the colony in the last decade of its existence; 4) they superficially reflect the circumstances of the colony; 5) it is necessary to generalize these circumstances in order to better understand life in the colony [25, P. 11].

Further, the author indicates that the source of her work is a collection of copies of letters of L.V. Tardent, sent to Switzerland and preserved there in the archives. H. Gander-Wolf has no more documents of this period at her disposal: “We could not find out with which of the representatives of the Russian government he [Tardent] was negotiating. It is only known that in the autumn of 1821 he wrote a letter to his fellow countrymen in which he asked them to go to Russia so that in the spring of 1822 they would start agricultural work in their new homeland” [25, P. 45]. Below we present some fragments of Tardent’s correspondence with Russian officials (with I.N. Inzov, Chief Trustee of the colonists of the southern region of Russia; with V.P. Kochubey, Minister of the Interior, and others), as well as excerpts from other archival documents that we received in research process.

In 1982, the Swiss Australian Jules Tardent published the book "The Swiss-Australian Tardent family history and genealogy" [29]. Excerpts from this book are used by journalist O. Grivat in describing the activities of L.V. Tardent in his work ([26], 1993).

Some fragments from the work of O. Grivat are used in the book by V.F. Onoprienko ([14], 2009). This book contains archival material, but its comments are mainly devoted to the achievements of the colonists and most often they are mere quotes from the book by E.I. Druzhinina [10] or literal translations from O. Grivat [26].

Thus, we see that all or almost all information relating to the personality of L.V. Tardent and his role in the development of Shabo, is based on his own letters and / or was published by his descendants A. Anselm and J. Tardent. It is no coincidence that in the film dedicated to the founding of the Shabo colony, which is being demonstrated to visitors at the Shabo Wine Culture Center, apart from Tardent no other name is mentioned, though it is matter of fact that development of viticulture and winemaking in Shabo was not his own exclusive prerogative.

Such an approach to reporting on events which took place almost two hundred years ago seems to us largely subjective. The documents we received from the Swiss, Ukrainian and Russian archives allow us to cast doubt on the current legend about the “daring scientist”, “friend of Pushkin and Pestalozzi” - Louis Vincent Tardent.

What was this man really?

According to the description of O. Grivat, with reference to J. Tardent, we learn this about the family of his famous ancestor: “Louis Vincent Tardent was the 10th child of Jacques David Tardent, from Ormont Dessus and his wife Marie Cherie. He was born on December 14, 1787 in Vevey, on January 4, 1788 he was baptized there. Louis Vincent Tardent died in 1836 in Chabag. His father, Jacques David Tardent, was an uninteresting, grouchy, and power-hungry man who sowed fear around him. He died of alcohol in 1825 ”[26, P. 11]. “L.V. Tardent’s grandfather, David Tardent, was an educated and respected man in the town of Vevey - regent² of the college, which he headed for 44 years and retired at 78 years. He died on 21/02/1820 ... David Tardent was one of the initiators of the school reform, an ardent admirer of J.J. Rousseau and his educational ideas ”[26, P. 12-13, see also 14, P. 17].

About L.V. Tardent O. Grivat writes: “Louis Vincennes Tardent received his education at the college in Vevey, where his grandfather worked. There, until 1813, he taught natural history (*histoire naturelle*) and calligraphy. He was a lover of music and singing, traded musical instruments. Then he opened a private school in order to better put into practice the teachings of Pestalozzi. Children of the local elite quickly began to relate to his students... ”[26, P. 11, see also 14, P. 17].

However, we find a slightly different description from J. Tardent (abbreviated text by the author): “Louis Vincent Samuel Tardent was the eldest son of Jacques David ... After graduating from elementary school, David (*grandfather of L.V. Tardent, a note by the Author*) sent his grandson at the Pestalozzi school in Yverdon, where he studied until 1804. In 1805, he began his studies at Parish College in Vevey. After its completion, on the recommendation of his grandfather, he was hired at the same school, where he worked until 1813, taught natural history and calligraphy... ”[29, P. 121].

“... Tardent was fond of music and singing and was on the board of the music society. He opened a music store, trading instruments. It was hard for him to feed his

2 Regent is a teacher at a primary school in Switzerland.

family. To this end, he opened a school, where he used to give additional lessons... ”[29, P. 122].

In his letters to Russian statesmen L.V. Tardent indicates his numerous titles: "Your humble servant, Tardent, agronomist, botanist, member of the Society of Swiss naturalists, naturalist, member of Swiss winegrowers in the canton of Vaud, adviser to one of the Swiss musical societies" [20, P. 2, 6, 13, 17; reverse sides of P. 30, 35].

The description of the merits of Tardent continues by O. Grivat: "... Louis Vincent Tardan is professor, botanist, winemaker, member of the Swiss Society of Natural Sciences, university member, man of high culture, ... partner and friend of an exceptional teacher Johann Heinrich Pestalozzi. He received his pedagogical training at the castle of Yverdon and corresponded with Pestalozzi until his death in 1827 ”[26, P. 10, see also 14, P. 17]. "J.H. Pestalozzi recommended Louis Vincent Tardent to Frédéric-César de La Harpe³ as a good teacher, scientist and fine winegrower", writes J. Tardent [29, P. 121] and H. Gander-Wolf, referring to the publication by A. Ansel, a descendant of L.V. Tardent [25, P. 38].

And here is what the official archive documents say (*abridged translation of the author*):

1. David Tardent, grandfather of L.V. Tardent, from November 1771, he worked as regent at school at the Parish College of Vevey. He taught in 5th grade. In the same school, in the 4th year, his eldest son Vincent worked, after the death of which in 1794 his father took over this class. David Tardent's youngest son worked in 5th grade. There is no information in the archives on the work of Louis Vincent Tardent in this school [16].
2. There is no document in the archives which would testify to the formation of Louis Vincent Tardent's own school. There is no date, no district, where this school would be after 1813 ”[15].
3. There is no document in the archives attesting that the Tardents were hereditary winemakers and had a direct or indirect relationship with the winemaking. They had no land around Vevey. In the land register of the municipalities around Vevey, there is no record of the presence of property belonging to the Tardent family, with the exception of a house in the Vieux Matzel district of Vevey [15, 18].
4. There is no information in the archives about the viticulture and wine-making education of L.V. Tardent, reported by Russian researchers V. Onoprienko et al., as well by J.Tardent, a descendant of L.V. Tardent. The only known fact is that he hails from the area between Lavaux and Castle of Chillon, which had been known as a wine-making area since the Middle Ages [15, 18].
5. The fact that Pestalozzi recommended L.V. Tardent to Frédéric-César de La Harpe, as a good teacher, scientist and excellent winegrower, is not confirmed with the archival documents [15].
6. Name of L.V. Tardent does not appear in the lists of students of the Pestalozzi school [17].

Let us also pay attention to the following fact: the private school of Pestalozzi in Yverdon (in some sources it is called the “institute”) existed from 1805 to 1825. [2,

3 Frédéric de la Harpe was the educator of Emperor Alexander I and came from the canton of Vaud. The Chabag settlement was organized with his participation.

P. 463]. Therefore, until 1804, as stated by J. Tardent (see above), his illustrious ancestor simply could not attend the Pestalozzi school.

Similarly in the process of working on the topic of our study, we did not find any information confirming the correspondence between Louis Tardan and Henry Pestalozzi “until his death”.

Descendants of L.V. Tardent call their famous ancestor also “a friend of A.S. Pushkin”.

In her documentary book [14] V.F. Onoprienko, referring to L.A. Chereysky ([22]) writes that “Friendship between A.S. Pushkin and L.V. Tardent was not interrupted (both of them were members of the Masonic Lodge in Chişinău)” [14, P. 18]. Indeed, both Tardent and Pushkin were members of the Ovid Masonic Lodge, No. 25 in Chişinău. But the statement about their mutual friendship is doubtful. On P. 430 in the book by L.A. Chereysky [22] there is a record concerning L.V. Tardent, to which V.F. Onoprienko makes her reference. However, there is no mention of any kind of friendship, and in particular about “uninterrupted” one. Perhaps the reference was used only to confirm the involvement of both in the Masonic lodge, and information about their friendship was taken from sources other than known to the Tardent descendants?

Without going into details regarding the interpretation of the concept of “friendship”, we turn to the opinion of Pushkin scholars.

The book of B.A. Trubetskoy “Pushkin in Moldova” [21] has a biographical dictionary. In this dictionary, the author placed the names of all people (245 persons) with whom Pushkin was familiar during the Chişinău exile (September 1820 - July 1823). Herein, four of them are defined as “friend” or “close friend”. Among others, under number 220 (alphabetically), this dictionary also contains an entry about L.V. Tardent: “The naturalist, Swiss, the founder of the colony in Shabo, which was visited by A.S. Pushkin in 1821. Tardent was also a member of the Masonic lodge “Ovid”, No. 25”. As can be seen, there is no mention of any friendly relations.

I.P. Liprandi⁴, accompanying the poet at his meeting with Tardent, recalled: “In the morning I wanted to see the Swiss Tardent, who had established a colony in the village of Shabo, three miles south of Akkerman. Pushkin came with me. He liked Tardent very much, and Tardent, who satisfied the countless questions of my companion, liked Pushkin. We stayed for two hours and took Tardent with us to dine with Nepenin. Having had lunch, we went to Izmail at six o’clock” [13, P. 306]. And here is an excerpt from the book by Yu.I. Druzhnikov: “Russian masonry was practically cut off from European Freemasonry and was coming to naught. And Pushkin was losing interest in it.

The only thing that brightened up his existence in the Chişinău desert were guests from abroad. He joyfully rushes to everyone, hoping to “breathe clean European air.” While Liprandi goes about his business on a business trip, Pushkin meets Louis Vincent Tardent, the founder of the Swiss colony of Shabo near Akkerman.

4 Liprandi, I.P. (1790-1880), major general, was a historian and a senior member of the secret police.

Apparently, Pushkin was very interested in understanding why a person escaped from where he wanted to go (*A.S. Pushkin did not receive permission to travel abroad and was "restricted to travel abroad" - author's note*). Tardent referred to the danger of the revolution, but it did not hurt Switzerland. They talked for two hours and did not find a common language. It turned out that Inzov persuaded Tardent to settle here, for the development of viticulture in the colony, promising assistance in the development of the case "[11, P. 159-160].

Obviously, under the "uninterrupted friendship" in the book of V.F. Onoprienko [14] random encounters are implied: in the epistolary heritage of A.S. Pushkin [19] we did not find a single letter to the "friend" Tardent.

Our study showed that L.V. Tardent was indeed a member of the Helvetic Society of Natural Sciences [30]. The conditions for participation in this society were as follows: 1) anyone who lives in Switzerland can be a member of the society; 2) membership of the society is gained as a result of secret ballot upon receipt of an absolute majority of votes; 3) a member of the society must have knowledge in the field of natural science; 4) entry fee - 6 francs.

In the document already mentioned above, L.V. Tardent is presented to the emperor as "a deputy of the Swiss winegrowers of the canton of Vaud." How did he become a deputy? Let us trace the chronology of events based on archived data. Upon learning about the settling of free lands in the south of Russia by foreign migrants from Jean François Saloz⁵, who worked as a veterinarian in Odessa for a long time, L.V. Tardent 19/12/1819 addresses with a letter to the plenipotentiary of the Bessarabian province, General A.N. Bakhmetyev: "I have the honor to inform you that my compatriot and friend Mr. Saloz, the head veterinarian of the Imperial Majesty in the southern provinces of the Russian Empire, has told me some details regarding the topographic features of Akkerman⁶ and the state-owned vineyards located there. He drew my attention to the fact that these neglected vineyards, almost abandoned today, with proper care and improvement, could after a few years bring great benefits to Russia" [6, P. 1-1 verso., 13]. Then he asks to transfer these vineyards to the ownership of 30 Vaudois vigneron⁷, "... so that we not only have the means, but also create a profitable and stable economy in this place" [ibidem].

At the same time, 22/12/1819, F. C. de la Harpe addressed the Russian Tsar Alexander I.: "...Mr. de Saloz said that a state vineyard grows in Bessarabia, which is greatly neglected. The vine growers of my country have been informed about this, and if the government gives their consent and permission, they will ask to allow them to work on these lands" [25, P. 39].

In a response letter to Tardent dated 30/04/1820 [20, p. 39-39 verso] A.N. Bakhmetiev promised him full support and patronage. The general also reported that he was ready to meet with his representatives from Odessa to inspect the land in order to explain to them all the advantages and disadvantages of the area.

Thus, having received the support of a representative of the local Russian government, 22.06.1820 L.V. Tardent informed officials of the canton of Vaud about

5 J.F. Saloz, like L.V. Tardent and F.C. de la Harpe Member of the Swiss Swiss Society of Natural Scientists.

6 Akkermann is a city in Bessarabia, today Belgorod-Dniesterovsky.

7 This refers to citizens from the canton of Vaud.

his plans, hoping to get a positive response from them. However, the Cantonal Council on 5.07.1820 rejected the proposal of L.V. Tardan, because it did not say anything about artisans, without whom, in their opinion, it was impossible to implement such a project [25, P. 44].

Despite the negative resolution of the Cantonal Council, Tardent went to Russia.

To do this, he managed to assemble a group of potential colonists. It included: Jean Lucien Gerry, Georges Amelli Testue, Jacob Samuel Chevalley and Francois Louis Petit. At a meeting organized on 13.08.1820 in Vevey, L.V. Tardent read letters to them, including the above letter of General A.N. Bakhmetyev dated 30.04.1820, as well as various documents regarding the foundation of the colony, expressing hope for a possible improvement in their financial situation. As the winegrowers were busy harvesting, the meeting decided to provide L.V. Tardent with the authority to act in the interests of the entire group and send him to Russia to inspect and evaluate the land.

For the trip he was given a loan of 800 francs, and at the end of 1820 the deputy went to the alleged location of the colony.

Upon arrival in Odessa 12.12.1820 L.V. Tardent addressed General A.N. Bakhmetyev with a request to send him to study the conditions under which the land will be provided to the Swiss colonists [6, P. 17-17 verso]. General A.N. Bakhmetiev, in his turn, informed the General Trustee and Chairman of the Board of Trustees of the Foreign Settlers of the Southern Territory of Russia, General I.N. Inzov, about the request of L.V. Tardent [6, P. 16-16 verso].

Having assigned all the responsibilities in relation to the settlement and arrangement of Swiss winegrowers near Akkerman upon General Inzov, A.N. Bakhmetyev also informed the Minister of Internal Affairs V.P. Kochubey [6, P. 19-19 verso, P. 24-24 verso]. V.P. Kochubey in his letter of March 24, 1821, in his turn, invited General Inzov "to give, at his discretion, an order regarding both the allotment of land to the Swiss and their disposition as well" [6, P. 19-19 verso, P. 24-24 verso].

During his personal meeting with L.V. Tardent General Inzov gave him a map, and granted him an opportunity to personally inspect the place for the Swiss to settle near Akkerman, where the state gardens promised by Alexander I were in disrepair.

After exploring the surroundings on 19 February 1821, L.V. Tardent submitted papers to general I.N. Inzov for transfer to the Russian emperor⁸, including: letters addressed to the general; description of Akkerman and its environs; copy of the mandate of L.V. Tardent, as a deputy of the Swiss winegrowers of the canton of Vaud, the Swiss obligation to the emperor, if they are resettled, as well as the Conditions mentioned above, upon approval of which the Swiss were ready to move to Russia, and which had been drawn up in Russia by L.V. Tardent. Copies of these documents were preserved in the archive [20].

These conditions consisted of 15 articles. Here is a brief description of them. In the first article, Tardent thanked the Emperor and asked if the Swiss could establish a colony.

8 For more details v. (5), Chap. 3.2.

The following three articles (2-4) were devoted to military service. It referred to exemption from military service. But, if someone wanted to voluntarily serve in the army, he must receive the same rights as the Russian nobles. This meant that they should receive privileges, rank and maintenance, as well as free themselves from hard work, like nobles.

Articles 5 and 6 referred to taxes. The Swiss must be exempted from all taxes for 20 years. After this period they will annually pay the taxes established by the Decree.

Article 7 reserved the right for everyone to leave the colony and the country.

Article 8 provided for each free lifetime possession of land.

Article 9 contained the desire of the Swiss to receive the patronage of the emperor and to serve only him.

Article 10 addresses organizational matters. The Swiss want a governor of their province who would directly report to the emperor.

Articles 11 and 14 deal with the free tax-free sale of products in the districts of Odessa and Akkerman, as well as the free use of wood from the surrounding forests, and its free transportation by land and water.

Articles 12–13 deal with the territorial issue. The shores from the Swiss colony are their property, and the colonists will independently protect them.

In Article 15 L.V. Tardent asks to give them an interest-free loan of 20,000 roubles for 10 years, necessary for the construction of a church, a house for a priest, a school, a boarding school and a pharmacy in Akkerman.

In a note to these conditions, depute Tardent wrote:

“If these conditions are not accepted, then the Swiss will refuse to relocate or will delay it for several years.”

The obligation of the Swiss to the emperor had the following text: “If they move to Russia and the colony is formed, the Swiss commit themselves to faithfully serve His Majesty the Emperor for his good nature” [20, P. 35 verso].

Of interest is also a letter of L.V. Tardent to count V.P. Kochubey dated 05.05.1821 [20, PP. 29-30], which stated in particular that the Swiss wanted to have advantages: enjoy freedom, as in Switzerland; to have a better attitude than to the Germans; so that they can enjoy the same rights as in Switzerland. Tardent asks the count to transmit this letter to the emperor, with hopes for his patronage, for this would encourage his fellow countrymen and himself.

According to the request of the Swiss, Count V.P. Kochubey reported to Alexander I and received the following command from him: “In order to accept these colonists on general rules, and with the same privilege which is assigned to other colonists, and regarding the land near Akkerman they are asking for, to demand information from Your Excellency (i.e. I.N. Inzov, author's note), as well as an opinion whether this land can be given to them... ” [6, PP. 27-27 verso].

As follows, we see that Emperor Alexander I does not accept the conditions put forward by Tardent, and with the approval of which the Swiss are ready to move to Russia.

Nevertheless, in a letter dated October 15, 1821 ([20, p. 79-79 verso]) L.V. Tardent personally expressed his gratitude to the emperor for recognizing the rights

of the Swiss to have the same privileges as the immigrants of other colonies enjoyed, and here he asked to give the Swiss immigrants an interest-free loan of 20,000 roubles for the construction of a church and a pharmacy. In response, the Russian Emperor Alexander I commanded “upon arrival and settling of the colonists, give them a loan for 10 years from Bessarabian income with payment of the indicated interest” [6, p. 34-35 verso]. Thus, this request of L.V. Tardent was not satisfied as well.

Despite the negative reaction of the Council of the canton of Vaud to the rejection by Emperor Alexander I of all the conditions and requests made by the representative of the “Vaudois vineyardmen”, as well as the fact that half of the existing vineyards have already been distributed to the local population (see below), L.V. Tardent did not stop his campaign work. In one of the letters already mentioned by us and cited by H. Gander-Wolf [25, P. 45], he, in particular, urged his comrades to set off immediately in order to begin the first work in the vineyards by spring of 1822. In another letter, he urges fellow countrymen not to seek “happiness in the unknown deserts and forests of North America, but to rush to the fertile lands of New Russia, where the vines, peaches, and mulberries ripen early and with great success” [1, P. 184].

Seeing that no one was going to budge, in April 1822 L.V. Tardent returned to Switzerland.

Upon arrival at his homeland, he reported to the meeting about his successful journey, talked about the “favorable results” that await them in the new place [24, P. 119]. He led heated debates, trying to convince his compatriots. After some time, this finally succeeded.

It is implied from a letter of L.V. Tardent written by him on June 25, 1822 to General I.N. Inzov, that potential colonists learned in their own country from a certain Russian master that they would be deceived in Russia. This was the reason for the loss of their interest and desire for relocation: “... The rumor raised by one of the Russians that we would be deceived, so discouraged my winegrowing companions that only the most reliable and courageous who really want to go remained. Others, more circumspect, want to wait and see how they will receive us, and how we will settle down on the lands allotted to us. ... Regarding me, who had the honor to meet you and fully trusts your favor, I will not hesitate and go on the road at the head of the first group (which I would call the backbone), consisting of 30-40 people of different ages, and I expect to arrive in mid-September ”[6, P. 41-41 verso, P. 59]. What is the reason for the stubbornness of Tardent during his deliberate deception of his countrymen - winegrowers and winemakers of the Swiss canton of Vaud? What prompted him to leave his country and draw such a large group of people into this adventure?

One of the versions can be found in E.I. Druzhinina’s work ([10, p. 147]: “... emigrants from” French “Switzerland settled on the right bank of the Dniester. They were prosperous winegrowers of the canton of Vaud, who left their native country partly because of land tightness, partly for political reasons.” And further, in a sub-footnote: “The liquidation of the Helvetic Republic in 1803 and the increasing dependence of Switzerland on France caused opposition from progressive circles.” As

can be seen from the list of the first colonists compiled by O. Grivat [26], all of them, with the exception of Tardent, were peasants: Chevalley was a hereditary winegrower and winemaker, the rest were hired workers of Tardent. The very same L.V. Tardent, a fairly educated person, and, as shown above, who did not have his own land, seems to us the most likely candidate for the role of the representative of these “progressive circles” who have to leave the country “for political reasons”.

H. Gander-Wolf on this occasion believes unambiguously: “The main motives for their resettlement were neither social, nor religious, but private-economic considerations” [25, P. 34]. The same thought, regarding L.V. Tardent, is expressed by his descendant J. Tardent: “... It was hard for him to feed his family. To this end, he opened a school where he gave additional lessons. ... Because of a happy circumstance, his life took a different direction... ” [29, P. 122]. And further in the text - about his move to Russia.

We also believe that it is precisely the opportunity to improve one’s financial situation that was the main reason for the resettlement of the future founders of the colony: there is little land in Switzerland, and it is very expensive. With 6-10 children in the family, nothing remains for the inheritance.

A peculiar version regarding the personal motives of Louis Vincent Tardent is given by A. Mavrokordato in the novel “Princess Tower” [27]. She points out that L.V. Tardent left Switzerland because his relatives accused him of setting fire to their house in order to steal the gold and the savings that they kept in that house. Naturally, fiction is not, and indeed cannot be, the basis for hypothesizing and for historical assumption. However, in this case, there is a small “but”: in one of his letters, Tardent himself, as the reason for his relocation, indicated disagreements with relatives, but did not want to talk about them [25, P. 38]. No other explanation given by Tardent himself was ever found in the documents⁹ available to us.

Another particularly interesting version does not refute all the previous ones and could explain Tardent's insistent desire to resettle and to diligently recruit his compatriots for this. Unfortunately, the State Archive of Odessa Region (Ukraine) and the Russian State Historical Archive located in St. Petersburg (Russian Federation) did not preserve the protocol of personal negotiations between Louis Vincent Tardent and the Chief Trustee and Chairman of the Board of Trustees on Foreign Settlers of the Southern Territory I. N. Inzov, dated 24. 08.1821. The lists of recruiting agents, as well as the payroll lists, were not found either. However, the New Year's greetings letter from L.V. Tardent to Count Vorontsov from 01.01.1830 with a message on the arrival of new families of Swiss colonists is well preserved. At the end of this letter, L.V. Tardent recalls that "... in November last year, my number was 62" [7, P. 23]. What is this number? It is known that the payment of recruiters, later the so-called government commissioners, depended on the number of people recruited. These government "messengers" conducted a powerful campaign in Switzerland to recruit people for resettlement to Russia [25, P. 27].

⁹ In the process of research we studied the documents on the topic, stored in the Russian State Historical Archive, St. Petersburg, Russia; State Archives of Odessa Region, Ukraine; State archive of the Kherson region, Ukraine; Izmail archive at the city executive committee, Ukraine; Archive of the Belgorod-Dniester Museum of Local Lore, Ukraine; Archive of Vevey, Switzerland (Archives communales Vevey); archives of the canton of Vaud, Switzerland (Archives cantonales vaudoises), as well as other documents (for details, see [5, Appendices]).

Therefore, we are inclined to believe that this could very well be the agent's personal number in the statement for receiving remuneration. Or, which also seems highly probable to us, is the number in the lists of agents paid for at the expense of the Russian state treasury and engaged in attracting foreign citizens to settle in colonies on the territory of the Russian Empire.

The group of the first settlers constituted 24 people, including children. In the early morning of July 19, 1822, nine large carts, each with 4 horses harnessed, set off from Vevey to the east. The march was led by the Tardents family with their children, followed by Jacob Samuel Chevalley from Riva with his family, then Charles Auguste Grange from Saint-Croix, Jean-Louis Gehry from Chebre, Jean-Louis Plantin - Tardent's clerk, Tardent's servant Francois Albertine Légeré, Henri Zwicky - an employee of Tardent from Karents (canton of Glarus), Louis Frederic Gügenen, Henri Berger from Avanches, Francois Noir from Lausanne [26, P. 22-23].

Despite all the hardships of the long journey of 2500 km., on 29 October 1822, after 103 days of travel, the future colonists arrived in Akkerman.

Immediately upon arriving at a new place, the colonists faced many difficulties. Arriving in Bessarabia at the end of October 1822, they received land only in March of the following year. However, after three weeks, part of the good land near Akkerman had to be ceded, and it was replaced by an allotment in the steppe, unsuitable for cultivation. The colonists received the land abandoned by the Turks, on which there were desolate, wild and overgrown vineyards.

At initial stage of cultivating the land they came across an old grapevine with the thickness of a hand, and its roots were thicker than a leg. Odessa officials did not give permission to pharmacist Berger to open his own pharmacy; the colonists could not obtain permission to build a tavern in the center of the village; they did not have the right to fish in the estuary, etc.

From the letters of Tardent it is clear that the Swiss needed everything. The funds brought from Switzerland were gradually spent, the colonists could not use the promised privileges, because they did not receive them. And here the question arises: did the people who followed Tardent to uncharted lands know that the conditions under which they were ready to move to Russia were not approved by the emperor?

In his report to General Inzov of June 21, 1823 Tardent wrote: "...In order to live this year, my comrades and I allowed the local peasants to cultivate our land in the hope that we could get some of the produce. But the papers that we sent you returned, having crossed out all our hopes and leaving us without a piece of bread for the winter. We beg your highness, our protector, to allow us to exercise our right. And since the harvest has already begun, ... we can lose everything and not subsequently gain what is appropriate for us..." [23].

Tardent reported that all their plans and hopes were destroyed: "The governor knows how much our trip and life for 18 months cost. He knows that we buy houses, animals, and he takes away from us what can help us to fill up the cracks, bring satisfaction to people who have hope for better welfare, but who are ruined..." [23].

Despite this, Tardent in almost every letter persistently urges his fellow countrymen to join the ranks of the citizens of Helvetianopolis¹⁰. In December 1822, a letter from L.V. Tardent was published in the Swiss Bulletin, in which he invites everyone to emigrate to Russia, invites to contact a certain Mr. Henry Aarburge, from whom they can receive the necessary documents and put themselves on the list [25, P. 49].

In his letter dated 18.05.1823, he wrote: "Oh, if you only knew how many unhappy people have found ways to live here! We in our Switzerland think that no country is better - this is a fallacy. There we get the fruits of labor, spending a lot of time and effort, and here the weather is beautiful almost all the time, fertile land, easily cultivated, a lot of cattle and at low prices. Winter has not been scary since 1812. There is little snow. Already in March, you can open and trim the vineyards "[23]. From a letter to Huguenin: "Our agricultural institution informs you of its consent to accept you into our company. We know that you and your sister are very decent people. You cannot refuse. But you are not a peasant. You will become the owner of 8 poses¹¹ vineyard and 200 poses of fields and meadows. What are you going to do? You need to bring good servants with you. ... Here are a few details about our institution that you can tell your friends. They will be able to get well-being not at distant lands. ... This is one of the rich countries. It never rains for more than two days, the sky is always clear, fruits, apricots, grapes bear fruit very well. There is a lot of bread that does not need to be looked for a long time. If you have enough bread, wine and an abundance of other products to be happy, hurry to come and share our calm position with us "[6, P. 426]. And gullible countrymen hurried to the "paradise" described by L.V. Tardent, but came across cruel reality.

From messages to Count M.S. Vorontsov: "The unfortunate colonists (fathers of 11 families) made a long journey from Switzerland here, at their own expense, that they sold their goods and left their homeland in order to find a second homeland here that would make them happy and which, they hope, would provide to them vineyards to shelter them from poverty and want! After a year of anticipation, and as their financial resources came to an end, they were finally provided with ten small vineyards, the profits from which could save them from starvation until next year; but this hope, this consolation was not long, because they had just been told that they should not touch the grape harvest! "[6, p. 301-302].

"These unfortunate ones received new vineyards only after 19 months and only one garden per person. And this is not enough to ensure your existence, because some of these gardens did not produce even 10 buckets of wine per year. Many of the newly arrived winegrowers completely went bankrupt and were forced to even sell their clothes in search of a piece of bread "[6, P. 426].

On December 18, 1826, the colonists in desperation turned to the Minister of the Interior V.S. Lansky "on the patronage of a colony of Swiss vineyards in the town of Shaba in Bessarabia" (v. Document 1¹²). They reported on the plight of newly

10 Originally a colony located in the settlement of Shabo and nearby territory, the colonists gave the name Helvetianopolis.

11 Pose is a French area measurement unit that corresponds to 0.45 ha.

12 Document 1 shows a fragment from the letter from the Swiss to the Interior Minister Graf W.S. Lanskoj, namely the signatures of the colonists [20, pp. 183-186].

arrived migrants who had not received gardens for months and were completely ruined, about the ban on the villagers from selling their homes to them, about their enmity with the “nomads” who drove their cattle to their fields and vineyards. “We asked for patronage from General Inzov, but we don’t see any results and therefore we ask you, Mr. Minister, for patronage and free us from fear and uncertainty. Our hope cannot be realized without your support and patronage, therefore we ask you to become our intercession to the emperor ”[20, P. 183-186].

*A Chaba in Helvétia in Bessebarie le 18^e
Decembre 1826*

Louis Tardent Haver
Guerry premier adjoint
George Destier adjoint
Charles Auguste Grand Jean
Henri Garbald
Jean Pierre Meillana
Jacob Samuel Chesalloy Daniel Besson
Jean Anthoine Mautard Jacques Gottraux
Jⁿ J^s Muller David Dupontais
Jean Louis Plantin Marc Tardent
Ed^{de} St. Huguenin Victor Lampiche
Francois Michon Louis Gaudin
Jean Francois Festin David Besson
Georges de Philippe Jorray Henry Lyke
Samuel Jancher Henri Chevalier

Document 1. Fragment of a letter from the Swiss settlers (signatures of the colonists) to Minister of the Interior Count V.S. Lansky [20, p. 183-186].

However, agitation continues. From a letter to the Stock family: “If you are still determined to become members of our community, you can come if you wish, provided that you are ready to fulfill the following circumstances: pay 150 rubles to establish a colony, and also undertake to exert all your strength for the prosperity of the colony. On the other hand, you will receive upon arrival 7-8 poses of vineyards and 200 poses of fertile land and privileges that guarantee the well-being of those who are economical and hardworking. You can have food here by cultivating your plot of land. I have good intentions to help you. I told Hippe and Maylard that we have the same intentions with you as with them. Talk to them so that you can come together ”[25, P. 65-63].

From the report of L.V. Tardent to M.S. Vorontsov, 27 July 1829: “My description of the land entrusted to the management of Your Excellency for rejecting my compatriots from resettlement in America and serving as foreign mercenaries

starts to produce some result, since I received a notice that some winegrower families are ready to leave Switzerland so that to go here ” [6, P. 446-446 verso].

The colonists also had a difficult relationship with the local population. The villagers released cattle into fields and vineyards, robberies and banditry flourished.

The colonists began to fight against the local population, who retained hostile feelings towards immigrants.

Already after his first visit to Russia, Tardent could not understand that the migrants would live not on a desert island, but with people whose mentality, language, customs and mores are alien to them and can be very difficult. Nevertheless, he deliberately provokes a future conflict. In the notes to the description of Akkerman and its environs already mentioned by us, intended for transmission to the emperor, L.V. Tardent wrote that "... there are 1,600 vineyards here, half of them have already been distributed," so he asks to transfer the second half of these vineyards to the Swiss. [...] Most of the local population does not have a permanent residence, and I did not dare to offer you to resettle these people. General I.N. Inzov himself suggested this to me... ”[20, P. 34-35.].

Further on, referring this time to the proposal of I.N. Inzov, he asks the emperor to relocate the local population to another territory, so that the nearby villages belong to the Swiss.

Bessarabian Vice Governor F.F. Wiegel, who came here in 1825, did not hide in his notes the fact that the rulers “ousted the previous inhabitants and transferred their immovable property to the aliens” [4].

This was the beginning of all subsequent conflicts, reaching the ongoing feuds between the Swiss colonists and the local population.

Both of them often wrote complaints. In a letter to General Inzov dated 6 June 1823, Tardent wrote: “Here are two requirements that we consider necessary to legitimize: 1. This applies to vines spoiled by animals on the territory of Shabo. Grazing animals without a shepherd and without special permission is strictly prohibited under the threat of a fine of one piastre ”[23]. As can be seen from the following documents, this petition of the colonists was not fulfilled, and they proceeded to self-defense.

From the statement of authorized residents of the village of Shabo to Count M.S. Vorontsov on 28 July 1826: “...Not content with a peaceful dwelling, Tardent himself or his younger son are shooting our cattle, and, looking at him, other his compatriots too, they eat it, up to thirty horned cattle and other various cattle had been slaughtered! The police drive us to live in the city... ” [6, P. 214]. After investigation the complaints of local residents were found to be substantiated, since in a short time L.V. Tardent killed 4 oxen, 8 cows, 4 calf, 7 pigs [6, P. 237 verso, P. 242].

Bessarabian Civil Governor V.F. Timkovsky in his report to M.V. Vorontsov on 9 October 1826 defended the local residents of Shabo. He accused the Swiss, especially Tardent, who, in his opinion, was guilty of all contentions "allowing himself, besides other harassment, the unlawful right to shoot the local residents' cattle running into their premises, not fenced by anything," [6, p. 236]. He further reported that the residents had finally lost their patience and were ready to avert violence by violence. In his opinion, these feuds will never stop, and, in order to

avoid serious consequences, he proposed to evict the Swiss to live in another place, and leave the peasants in Shabo.

In 1829, an epidemic broke out in Shabo. Russian soldiers who were returning from the war of 1828-1829 with Turkey were stationed in the village. The soldiers brought the plague into the village, which mercilessly devastated the Swiss settlement. Each house in the village was in mourning, almost half of the colony consisted of widows and orphans. In the winter of that year, an earthquake struck here.

As can be seen, in the new place the "favorable results" promised by L.V. Tardent, did not expect the Swiss colonists but poverty, hunger and hostile environment: constant battles against the local population, which maintained hostile feelings towards the aliens, as well as the biased attitude of officials. In such external conditions, complete disharmony began in the relationship between the colonists themselves, to internal conflicts, which were much worse than external adversities.

The State Archive of Odessa Region preserved a document dated 21 September 1836, translated from French, "The order of the village council of the Shabo colony to the colonists of the same colony Charles, Samuel and Louis Tardent to stop damaging the vegetable gardens and haystacks of other colonists and not to let livestock into other people's gardens". The document refers to the numerous complaints of the colonists about the significant harm done to them, the damage to their gardens and haystacks caused by the Tardent brothers. Despite repeated verbal orders, the brothers did not think about stopping such disturbances, so the village council¹³ was forced to inform the Board of Trustees about this.

"You need to be reminded", the document goes on to say, "what you did with the cattle which entered your late father's garden. This is common knowledge. The colonists, in turn, had the right to act now in the same way with your cattle, but they were indulgent towards you "[8, d. 4334, p. 2].

The Swiss colonists were disappointed to the extreme: nostalgia for their homeland, hard work, dishonest officials, envy and hostility of the local population, epidemic of plague, invasion of locusts, drought, famine, etc., etc. So the colonists completely went bankrupt. They left their homeland to become disappointed in the unfulfilled hopes for the best and die in a foreign land.

The children of the colonists, before the construction of a four-year parish school in 1830, did not have the opportunity to study. Unlike the rest of the children of the first generation colonists, the children of L.V. Tardent had the opportunity to receive an education. Tardent taught them himself. His son, Charles Tardent, continued his education in Switzerland, where he studied "viticulture, botany, agriculture, horticulture. After the death of his father in 1836, Charles Tardent returned to Shabo, significantly replenishing his knowledge "[14, p. 28].

13 Before the reform of 1861, the village council (prikaz) included elected officials: village headman, tax collector and clerk. In the Swiss colony of Shabo, these functions were performed by the mayor and his two assistants, elected for three years. In 1836, Philippe Louis Julius Hächler held the post of mayor, his assistants were F. Melieu and F. Testuz, who in 1835-1837 constituted the council of the Shabo colony.

However, not all were in need in Shabo. The rapid growth of wealth was observed during this period in the economy of Louis Vincent Tardent. For 1828-1834, i.e. for 6 years, his family acquired 100 thousand vines, his son Mark Tardent - 25 thousand vines. In 1828, in the ownership of L.V. Tardent there were 3317 forest and mulberry trees, Mark Tardent had 2441. For comparison: Georges Testu had 210 trees, and Charles Grangean had 125 [8, d. 2407, l. 30-31; d. 3673, l. 170-170 verso]. In 1834, in the gardens and plantations of L.V. Tardent there were 5 thousand mulberries of different varieties, 3 thousand forest trees, 2 thousand poplars and willow trees, 2 thousand walnuts, 4 thousand fruit trees of the best varieties, 5 thousand bushes of different varieties, 120 thousand grape bushes, planted over 8 years, of which 46 thousand gave wine, 100 thousand grape seedlings planted in the spring of 1834 [8, d. 3616, l. 2].

L.V. Tardent sold his house in Vevey on 25 May 1822 for 8750 francs [25, p. 47]. For this money, he could get in a Swiss bank 2.54 kg. gold. It is suggestive of what contributed to such prosperity and the rapid growth of the wealth of the family of L.V. Tardent, and at the same time the impoverishment of other colonists - hereditary winegrowers and winemakers?

Until 1831 L.V. Tardent remained the head of the settlement, appointed by the Governor of Bessarabia, General I.N. Inzov. After that, the administration of the colony passed to the collective body, headed by the mayor. From the beginning of the 30s of the XIX century, the welfare of Shabo continuously grew, and, thanks to hard work, the will and desire of the colonists to survive, in the 80s the colony reached its economic and cultural heyday and continued until the outbreak of the First World War in 1914. Following the results of World War I, Bessarabia, including the Swiss colony of Shabo, moved to Romania.

The Molotov-Ribbentrop Pact put an end to the existence of the Swiss colony of Shabo: in the autumn of 1940, most of the colonists left the village of Shabo and went to their historical homeland - to Switzerland. About 39 families did not leave the colony. Their property and land were expropriated and transferred to the state farm.

In accordance to data on the census of the village of Shabo in the Liman volost of Akkerman district for 1941, which are kept in the archive of Izmail, Ukraine, two people were deported to Russia, 15 families went to Germany [12]. This archive, as well as the Information Service of the Republic of Moldova, the State Archive of Odessa Region and the Office of the Security Service of Ukraine in Odessa Region do not have information (except for 3 people) on the fate of the remaining 21 families.

Some of the descendants of the Tardent family emigrated to America, Australia in the 1880s, and to Switzerland in 1940. The fate of the families of Paul and Adrien Tardent, who remained in Shabo, together with the fate of the remaining 19 Swiss families, remained unclear.

Thus ended the story of the Swiss colony of Shabo, the richest colony in Russia at the end of the 19th century.

So who is he, Louis Vincent Tardent? Hero? Provoker? Benefactor? Adventurer? Perhaps the truth, as often happens, is somewhere in between.

Our task in this work was to, based on archival data and materials from publications, depict the first head of the Shabo colony from a slightly different angle than it is traditionally rendered. And the picture obtained casts doubt on the prevailing legend of the “impudent scientist,” “the friend of Pushkin and Pestalozzi,” Louis Vincent Tardent.

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This article was first published in Ukrainian in 2011.

Гетте Г., Молотков Г. Луї Вінсен Тардан: погляд з іншого ракурсу //Чорноморський літопис. – 2011. – Вип. 3. – С. 52 - 61.

English translation was made by the Author.